

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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POSTANESTHESIA HANDOFF: AN
EVIDENCE-BASED QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Patient handoffs between healthcare providers occur multiple times a day. Poor communication during these transitions of care may jeopardize patient safety. Standardization of handoffs and the use of cognitive aids, such as checklists, can improve communication and prevent errors. Studies show that incorporating the use of checklists in preoperative and intraoperative care reduces morbidity and mortality. The purpose of this project was to improve patient handoff communication between anesthesia providers and post-anesthesia care unit (PACU) staff through the implementation of a standardized handoff checklist.

This quality improvement (QI) project occurred at a large urban academic medical center in the perioperative department. A committee comprised of anesthesiologists and certified registered nurse anesthetists (CRNAs) with consultant registered nurses (RNs) from the post-anesthesia care unit developed a cognitive aid checklist using available literature and considering the practice setting, patient population, and department culture. To assess baseline information on handoff processes, the author conducted patient handoff observations using the checklist tool. The committee offered all anesthesia staff training on a safe patient handoff and the new checklist procedure. The author conducted a post-training assessment of knowledge acquisition and observations of the application of patient handoffs.

The sample consisted of 195 anesthesia providers (36 SRNAs, 28 CRNAs, 55 residents and 76 anesthesiologists) received education related to the checklist via email; approximately 76 also participated in face-to-face training (36 SRNAs, 20 CRNAs, and 20 residents). Prior to the training, the author conducted 68 handoff observations; none

included all required checklist elements. Only 65 providers completed the pre- or post-training knowledge and attitude survey (response rates, 27.2%, 6.2% respectively). In post-training handoff observations assessments of information transfer and checklist use, only 10.9% of the providers used the checklist during their handoff report.

A comparison of the pre- and post-knowledge and attitude surveys did not support the educational training influencing the knowledge and skills of the providers regarding safe handoff practices. Responses to these two surveys were poor and, in fact, may reflect a lack of buy-in of the project by the stakeholders. From pre- to post-training only a 4% increase in information transferred during handoffs occurred. However, a post-training comparison of handoffs with and without checklist use revealed a 21.6% increase in information transfer when staff used the checklist.

The project revealed that further examination of the barriers to quality improvement implementation and strategies for staff participation in practice change is necessary. Lessons learned during the process include the need for increased time and resources in the planning phase to aid in the implementation of a QI project in large public, academic medical centers. In future QI projects, the author recommends researching strategies to improve staff input and senior staff buy-in and support. Considering incentives for phases throughout implementation is suggested.

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INTRODUCTION

Handoffs occur multiple times a day for patients, and these transitions of care have the potential for poor communication which compromises patient safety (Potestio, Mottla, Kelley, & DeGroot, 2015). Communication errors during the transfer of care occur for many reasons. Some of these may be human factors such as inexperience, information degradation and miscommunication, lack of standardization, production pressure and environmental distractions. These circumstances could increase sentinel events, medication errors, and poor patient outcomes (Robins & Dai, 2015). An astonishing 80% of medical mistakes occur because of communication failure during the transition of patient care (Robins & Dai, 2015).

High reliability organizations, like the aviation industry, use checklists as a tool to decrease errors and increase safety. Healthcare is increasing in complexity, necessitating changes to maintain patient safety. Standardization of handoff and the use of cognitive aids, such as checklists, can mitigate human factors that lead to error. Studies show that incorporating standardized checklists in preoperative and intraoperative care is linked to a significant reduction in morbidity and mortality (Haynes et al., 2009). Also, improved handoff communication is a National Patient Safety Goal, and The Joint Commission requires handoff standardization, including two-way communication (Arora & Johnson, 2006).

A large public, academic medical center with no current standard for perioperative handoffs was the setting for this evidence-based practice quality improvement project. In addition to the above mentioned human factors that can lead to

communication failure, this institution sees a high staff turnover rate and the academic setting experiences a regular influx of new providers.

Prior to the initiation of this DNP project, a survey of the anesthesia staff revealed that the majority of providers agreed that handover affects patient safety. However, 65% did not agree that they received formal training in this process and over 30% did not feel handoffs were performed systematically. In addition, structured observations of 54 baseline patient handoffs revealed some information was regularly transferred (e.g., age, allergies, surgery, analgesics, antiemetics, and antibiotics). Other information not regularly transferred included patient name, diagnosis, American Society of Anesthesiologist (ASA) classification, and language preference. Additionally, the author did not consistently observe an opportunity for clarification and questions between handoff partners or an ID band check of the patient.

Thus, the purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to improve patient handoff communication between anesthesia providers and post-anesthesia care unit (PACU) staff through the implementation of a standardized handoff checklist.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Model for Improvement

Successfully implementing an effective process change requires careful planning and execution. A supporting framework is an invaluable tool to guide a quality improvement project such as the one planned by the author to improve perioperative transitions of care. A framework helps to create structure and guide a team through the process of improving performance. The Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) endorses The Model for Improvement for rapid change cycles focused on improving care quality. This model includes two parts; first is three fundamental questions and second is the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycle (Langley, Moen, Nolan, & Nolan, 2009). The PDSA cycle is an iterative process that incorporates pilot testing of small practice changes to promote quality improvement efforts (Langley et al., 2009).

Model for Improvement, Part One

The PDSA model begins with having the clinician(s) answer three questions (Langley et al. 2009).

1. What are we trying to accomplish?
2. How will we know that a change is an improvement?
3. What change can we make that will result in improvement?

The author used the IHI (2017) science of improvement framework to acknowledge key issues to address in responding to each of the three questions before implementation of this project. Question one sets the aims for the project. The answer to this question should include time-specific and measurable goals and a setting for the project. The goal of this project was to improve communication and information

transmission during the transfer of patient care. The second question compels the team to establish measures to determine how they will assess for improvement. Measures need to be quantitative to allow for evaluation. In addition to the handoff survey, the author conducted a post-training handoff survey using the same 5-point Likert scale questionnaire. The observation tool with a score of 1 for positive transfer of information and 0 for lack of transfer of information utilized for the baseline data collection was used to quantify post-training information transfer. The planned change to improve communication between providers in the post-anesthesia setting was the implementation of the checklist.

Model for Improvement, Part Two

The PDSA cycle includes four constructs: plan, do, study and act. *Plan* is the construct for developing the learning opportunity, test or implementation (Langley et al., 2009). It includes what questions to address, the anticipated answers and a data collection strategy (Langley et al., 2009). For this project, the team assessed the current practice and conducted a review of the literature. Relevant research was utilized to develop a checklist and an education module for the staff. Included in this was the plan for implementation and data collection. The execution of the plan is the construct for *do*. The PDSA cycle also involves observation and data collection which must include any unanticipated effects (Langley et al., 2009). During this phase, the staff received training on transitions of care and the use of the checklist. The author conducted handoff observations to evaluate the effectiveness of the new process. The *study* construct compares the data collection with the expectations and studies the results (Langley et al., 2009). The appropriate action derived from the knowledge gained during the study portion is the *act*

construct (Langley et al., 2009). The model for improvement is easy to follow and adaptable for various forms of improvement projects.

Figure 1. Model of Improvement (based on information from Langley et al., 2009).

Figure 2. PDSA Cycle (based on information from Langley et al., 2009).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This QI project aimed to improve communication and increase information transfer during handoff in the PACU. To assure the most recent and reliable information guided this project, the author conducted a review of the literature focusing on patient handoff and communication. The following electronic databases were utilized to search for relevant publications: CINAHL, PubMed, PsycINFO (EBSCO), Web of Science and Google Scholar. The umbrella topics for the literature search included patient handover and interdisciplinary communication. Additional terms included anesthesia, post-anesthesia, post-anesthesia care unit, checklist, perioperative, multidisciplinary, communication and teamwork. The author limited all searches to peer-reviewed articles published in English and reviewed articles by title, abstract and for applicability to this project.

Patient handoff is the “transfer of information and professional responsibility and accountability between individuals and teams” (Jeffcott, Evans, Cameron, Chin & Ibrahim, 2009, p.272). There is an extensive discussion in the literature about patient handoff and the transfer of information and responsibility from one healthcare provider to another. Though the focus of this project was on interdisciplinary healthcare providers in the operating room and post-anesthesia care unit, it is clear throughout the literature that regardless of specialty or discipline, handoffs are often unstructured, inconsistent, and incomplete.

Each transfer has the potential for communication failures and threats to patient safety. Patients undergoing surgery are especially vulnerable for multiple reasons. Throughout the perioperative process, the surgical patient is exposed to a high number of handoffs, therefore increasing the likelihood of errors (Nagpal et al., 2011). Handoffs

commonly occur within professional groups. Though throughout the perioperative process including the postoperative phase, handovers transpire between providers of different disciplines (Nagpal et al., 2010). Also, during the postoperative and post-anesthesia period, the patient's physiological status is susceptible to potentially rapid and severe changes (Randmaa, Swenne, Mårtensson, Högberg, & Engström, 2016).

In 2006 one of the Joint Commission on Accreditation of Healthcare Organization's National Patient Safety Goals was to improve the effectiveness of communication among caregivers, requiring hospitals to implement handover communication standardization including two-way communication (Arora & Johnson, 2006). Despite this goal, a systematic review of the literature conducted by Segall et al. (2012) reveals that handoffs are often not standardized and of inadequate quality. While research in this area is still in the early stages, some recommendations have been widely supported in the literature (Segall et al., 2012). Standardization, which includes the "use of checklists to guide communication and protocols to structure clinical activities" (Segall et al., 2012, p. 110), is most notably advocated by researchers. Other recommendations include minimizing tasks and distractions during verbal handover and only discussing patient-specific information (Segall et al., 2012). Segall et al. (2012) advocated two-way communication including the time for each provider involved to speak and ask questions. An additional common theme found in the literature is communication and team skills training for providers (Segall et al., 2012). The technique of a multimodal approach to improving handoffs was found to increase handoff effectiveness significantly and was also noted to have an apparent effect three years later (Weinger et al., 2015).

As there is extensive literature on patient handover, there is also extensive literature on communication. A review of key studies reveals that communication errors are far too common and occur in all phases of perioperative care (Greenberg et al., 2007). One study on operating room (OR) communication found that about 30% of exchanges between team members included communication failures, a third of which caused a threat to patient safety (Lingard et al., 2004). Specific to the recovery period, Nagpal et al. found that 14% of adverse events occurred secondary to communication failures in the handover process.

Similar to the literature available on patient handovers, the literature on communication reveals that ineffective communication is a problem that can lead to medical errors (Lingard et al., 2004). It is noted that some of the flaws with communication in the OR may be due to lack of standardization and team integration (Lingard et al., 2004). In parallel with handoff literature, the studies on communication recommend information standardization with the use of checklists (Nagpal et al., 2010). Additional recommendations to improve communication are to implement protocols and care pathways and to utilize electronic communication systems and proforma documents (Nagpal et al., 2010).

The literature also includes discussion on the applicability of strategies used by high reliability organizations, such as space shuttle mission control, nuclear power, railroad dispatching and ambulance dispatching in the healthcare setting. While differences exist, these settings have similarities to the healthcare environment. An HRO is “made up of complex, interconnected systems, and are event-driven, time-pressured, and resource-constrained while having the potential for high consequences for system

failure,” (Patterson, Roth, Woods, Chow, & Gomes, 2004, p. 130). Knowledge gained from examining and understanding their communication and coordination strategies can be utilized to develop policies for improvements in the healthcare setting (Patterson et al., 2004).

There is a consensus throughout the literature that patient handoffs are unstructured, inconsistent, often including communication failures, and that these are threats to patient safety. The most widely noted recommendations for improvement in communication are standardization and the use of cognitive aids. While no one standardized handoff protocol is appropriate for all disciplines and specialties, the recommendation is to develop and tailor protocols to meet the needs of the providers and the patient population within each department.

METHODS

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to improve patient handoff communication between anesthesia providers and post-anesthesia care unit (PACU) staff through the implementation of a standardized checklist. This chapter presents the design, setting, sample, measures, procedures, and analysis plan.

Design

An evidence-based practice QI project was designed to implement and evaluate a standardized handoff process. The goal was to improve communication and increase information transfer from the operating room anesthesia staff to the PACU staff. Pre- and post- intervention surveys were used to evaluate the effectiveness of the handoff checklist.

Setting

This setting for this project was a single hospital facility. This large 600-bed, level one trauma center serves 10 million residents. It is a non-profit county hospital in a lower socioeconomic urban area. Patients are primarily Hispanic, and many are non-English speaking. The hospital has 25 main operating rooms and a 15-bed post-anesthesia care unit.

Sample

The convenience sample of subjects included all anesthesia providers at the author's place of employment, e.g., attending anesthesiologists, resident anesthesiologists of all levels (clinical anesthesia (CA) 1, CA2, and CA3), certified registered nurse anesthetists (CRNAs), and student registered nurse anesthetists (SRNAs). The CRNAs are all full-time employees of the hospital working a minimum of 36 hours per week on

site. Approximately 85% of the attending anesthesiologists divide their clinical time between two medical centers (public/county and private). Anesthesia residents spend the majority of their first-year training at this facility. After the initial training period, they rotate to different hospitals for additional experience. Similarly, half of the new SRNA class spend their first or second 4 months of clinical training at the county setting and then rotate to different hospitals and specialty areas.

An anesthesiology department perioperative handoff committee was formed consisting of the author and four anesthesia providers. In addition, a PACU RN and the PACU charge RN consulted on the project to promote interdisciplinary communication and continuity of patient care. The goal of the committee was to develop department policies for the transfer of patient care. The team members supported practice improvement and agreed to ensure the necessary resources for project implementation.

Ethical Issues

The Institutional Review Board from the author's place of employment and California State University, Long Beach (CSULB) granted approval.

Checklist

Prior to the initiation of this DNP project the author developed a cognitive aid checklist (Appendix A) using the available literature and considering the setting, patient population, and department culture. The checklist originally included 20 items reflecting salient information to communicate during the transfer of care. While the patient ID check including verification of the ID band is a necessary step in the transfer of care, data collection revealed that the middle of the verbal handoff report was not an ideal time for this step. Therefore, it was removed from the observation data analysis converting the

original 20-item checklist to the 19-item checklist as described here. Three CRNAs including the Chief CRNA, an anesthesiology resident, two PACU RNs including the primary PACU charge nurse and the Chief of the Anesthesiology Department established face validity of the checklist. The checklist includes items such as age, surgery, past medical history, and type of anesthesia. The checklist also incorporates indicators of closed-loop communication including assuring that the receiver is ready to begin and that both team members have an opportunity to speak and ask questions during the exchange.

Measures

The handoff committee used available literature and previous projects at the author's location of employment as models to create a handoff knowledge and attitudes survey (Appendix B) and an observation tool (Appendix C) for use in this project (Franco, 2015; Potestio, 2015). The observation tool included the 19-items on the checklist. The tool allowed the observer to score each item as a 1 for information transferred, or 0 for information not transferred. The author converted both tools into an electronic format, (Qualtrics®), for data collection purposes and ease of use by the staff.

The CRNA members of the handoff committee developed the handoff survey (Appendix B) to assess staff's experiences and confidence related to handoff processes. The team adapted the survey from one previously developed by members of the handoff committee during their Educational Doctorate training (Cole, 2015; Franco, 2015; Garcia, 2015). It included eight Likert questions (strongly disagree [1], disagree [2], neither agree nor disagree [3], agree [4], or strongly agree [5]; range 8-40). Examples of questions included; "I have received formal training on how to give handoff report, and "I am confident in my ability to provide an effective handoff report." Five experts in anesthesia

reviewed the tool to establish face validity. The tool was piloted before this DNP project with 62 anesthesia providers (CRNAs, attending anesthesiologists, resident anesthesiologists, SRNAs) and found to be intuitive and feasible. Handoff survey scores are summed for a total score (range 8-40). An additional four questions (Appendix D) regarding the training and new process were added to the survey after project implementation concluded.

The author observed the handoff process between providers before and after the implementation of the educational module using the second tool (Appendix C). This tool includes nineteen observation points which reflect each item on the handoff checklist (Appendix A, C). For analysis purposes, the item was scored as present if the information was exchanged between providers, regardless of whether the individual giving report voluntarily reported the information or the RN receiving report requested the information. The CRNA handoff committee members and another CRNA colleague established face validity of the tool.

Procedures

The author created the checklist tool digitally on Qualtrics® to record information transferred during the patient handoff. The author stood close enough to hear the handoff process but did not self-identify the purpose of her placement. It is normal for a CRNA to be present in the PACU for the monitoring and care of patients in the PACU. If staff questioned the author's presence, she informed them of the data collection. No blinding took place; the observer was within hearing distance and visible to staff members. The author conducted post-training data collection with the same methods as pre-training observations. The author observed 54 handoffs during February and March of 2016 and

an additional 14 handoffs during June and August of 2017 before the educational intervention.

Anesthesia providers received the educational content, through in-person lectures (Appendix E) at regular department meetings depending on their availability to attend these meetings. Because not all providers were able to attend one of the lectures or were unable to stay for the duration of the presentation, email distribution to all providers also occurred to ensure that everyone in the purposive sample received educational content (Appendix F) about the checklist and the project. The face to face presentations lasted from 15-45 minutes, depending on the attendee's level of experience and time allotted by the administration. The emails contained content similar to the presentations, with more thorough PowerPoint slides and typed narration under the slides to include the verbal content contained in face to face training. Checklist distribution occurred electronically to all anesthesia providers, and every computer station in the PACU had a laminated copy posted. After the completion of trainings, the author repeated handoff observations in November and December of 2017. Staff members completed a knowledge and attitudes handoff survey, modified from existing tools (see Measures), before and after the training (Appendix B, D).

Data Analysis

Quality metrics evaluated the effectiveness of the checklist on information transferred.

- 1) Percent of complete handoffs
 - a. Numerator: Number of complete handoffs (all information transferred)
 - b. Denominator: Total number of handoffs

- 2) Percent of checklist items transferred
 - a. Numerator: Number of items transferred from the handoff list
 - b. Denominator: Number of items on the handoff list
- 3) Percent of handoffs that include the item “assess for readiness”
 - a. Numerator: Number of handoffs including “assess for readiness”
 - b. Denominator: Total number of handoffs
- 4) Percent of handoffs that include “do you have any questions”
 - a. Numerator: Number of handoffs including “do you have any questions”
 - b. Denominator: Total number of handoffs
- 5) Percent of items transferred with checklist use (post-training)
 - a. Numerator: Number of items transferred when checklist used
 - b. Denominator: Number of items on the handoff list

Measures of central tendency describe sample characteristics (numbers and percentages; means, ranges, standard deviations). Changes in knowledge and attitudes pre- and post-training were analyzed using inferential statistics.

RESULTS

Handoff observations and the knowledge and attitudes survey, both conducted pre- and post-training are the two measures used for analysis. Results are reported separately for clarity.

Handoff Observations

During opportuneness times, the author conducted observations of SRNAs, CRNAs, and residents. Attending anesthesiologists do not routinely provide handoff in the PACU and therefore were not included in observations. The author conducted a total of 123 pre- and post-training structured handoff observations, though the number of individual providers observed is unknown as identifying data were intentionally not collected.

Several metrics evaluated the quality of the handoff processes (information transferred). The first quality metric was the percent of handoffs that contained all the items on the checklist. The author conducted 55 post-training handoff observations. Before the training and the introduction of the checklist, no handoffs included all the items on the checklist. After the introduction of the checklist, two handoffs (3.6%) contained all items on the checklist.

The second metric was the percent of items transferred from the checklist during each handoff. Pre-training the percent of items transferred from the checklist was 65%, with a mean of 12.33 items transferred (Table 1). After the education and introduction of the checklist, the percentage of items transferred increased to 69%, with a mean of 13.18 items transferred (Table 1).

Metrics three and four were utilized to assess the impact of the training on closed-loop communication. The third quality metric was the percent of handoffs that included an assessment of staff readiness to initiate the handoff (metric 3). The fourth quality metric was the percent of handoffs that included the confirmation of clarification or questions (metric 4). With training and the use of the checklist, the assessment of readiness for handoff decreased from 85% to 80% while the check for clarification or questions increased from 36% to 55% (Table 3).

The fifth quality metric evaluated the effectiveness of the checklist in transferring information. Comparing the mean number of items transferred when staff did not use the checklist with the mean number of items transferred when staff used the checklist during post-training observations measured checklist effectiveness. Without the checklist, a mean of 12.7 items (66.8%) was transferred, with the use of the checklist a mean of 16.8 items (88.4%) was transferred, a 21.6% increase in information transfer (Figure 3).

Table 1

Quality Metrics Related to Checklist Use

	Pre-training n (%)	Post-training n (%)
Number of complete handoffs (metric 1)	0 (0%)	2 (3.6%)
Number of handoffs that included “Assess for readiness” (metric 3)	58 (85%) ^a	44 (80%)
Number of handoffs that included “do you have any questions?” (metric 4)	24 (36%) ^b	30 (55%)
Mean number of items transferred (metric 2)	12.33 (65%)	13.18 (69%)

number of items [18-19] on the checklist [denominator]; ^an=67; ^bn=68; ^cn=55

Figure 3. Effectiveness of checklist on information transfer (metric 5)

Knowledge and Attitude Surveys

One hundred ninety-five anesthesia providers received education related to the checklist via email (36 SRNAs, 28 CRNAs, 55 residents and 76 anesthesiologists). Seventy-six of the providers (39% of the total sample) also attended a face to face training (36 SRNAs, 20 CRNAs, and 20 residents). Fifty-three participants completed the Knowledge and Attitudes (K&A) survey before the training (response rate 27.2%), and 12 completed the survey after the training (6.2% response rate) (Table 2). Table 2 displays the classifications of the trainees who choose to complete the K&A survey. K&A scores did not improve with the training (pre-training mean 30.02 [range 17-x36, 4.63] to post-training mean 29.92 [range 14-36, 6.10], $p=0.948$). Linking of individual scores between pre- and post-training was not possible because of the low response rate and the variation among providers choosing to complete each survey.

Participants demonstrated an increase in K&A mean scores from pre-training to post-training on four questions. These questions focused on provider confidence (Q2), receipt of training (Q3), adequate time for handoff (Q6) and the clarity of patient care recommendations (Q9). However, the respondent scores of four questions decreased (moved in a direction that is counterintuitive to the project). These questions focused on patient safety (Q4), delivery in a systematic fashion (Q5), distractions (Q7) and clarification (Q8) (Table 3). Eight of the 12 respondents reported post-training that they neither agree nor disagree that they gained knowledge from the training module (Figure 4).

Table 2

Classification of Survey Participants

	Pre Training (N = 53)	Post Training (N = 12)
CRNA ¹	7 (13%)	6 (50%)
SRNA ²	24 (45%)	2 (17%)
CA-1 ³	3 (6%)	1 (8%)
CA-2 ⁴	4 (7%)	0
CA-3 ⁵	1 (2%)	0
Attending Anesthesiologist	13 (25%)	3 (25%)
PGY-1 ⁶	1 (2%)	0

¹ CRNA= Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetist, ² Student Registered Nurse Anesthetist, ³Clinical Anesthesiologist 1, ⁴ Clinical Anesthesiologist 2, ⁵Clinical Anesthesiologist 3, ⁶Post Graduate Year 1.

Table 3

Knowledge and Attitudes Survey

	Pre-intervention n=53 Mean (range, SD) ¹	Post Intervention n=12 Mean (range, SD)	<i>p</i> ²
Q2 - I am confident in my ability to provide an effective PACU handoff report	3.81 (1-5, 1.33)	3.83 (1-5, 1.47)	0.96
Q3 - I have received formal training in providing a PACU handoff report	2.77 (1-5, 1.23)	3.25 (2-4, 0.97)	0.22
Q4 - The PACU handoff report affects patient safety	4.56 (1-5, 0.80)	4.25 (1-5, 1.14)	0.23
Q5 - The PACU handoff report is delivered in a systematic fashion	3.74 (1-5, 0.88)	3.58 (1-5, 1.24)	0.62
Q6 - Adequate time is allotted for an effective PACU handoff report	3.52 (1-5, 0.98)	3.75 (1-4, 0.87)	0.46
Q7 - The PACU handoff report is delivered with minimal distractions	3.35 (1-5, 0.98)	2.83 (1-4, 1.12)	0.20
Q8 - Asking if there are any questions, comments, or concerns is an important part of the PACU handoff report	4.56 (2-5, 0.63)	4.25 (1-5, 1.14)	0.17
Q9 - Recommendations are made clear during the PACU handoff report	3.83 (1-5, 0.94)	4.17 (3-5, 0.58)	0.24

¹SD=Standard deviation. ²Mann-Whitney

Figure 4. Agreement with the statement on the evaluation: "I gained knowledge from the training module."

Figure 5. Agreement with the statement on the evaluation: "I am using the checklist for handoff in the PACU" and "I believe the new process is effective and promotes patient safety."

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this project was to improve information transfer during patient handoffs between anesthesia providers and post-anesthesia care unit (PACU) staff through the implementation of a standardized handoff checklist. In this QI project, the use of the checklist and educational training resulted in a minimal overall increase in the amount of information transferred during handoffs (Table 1). This increase was less than that found by Potestio et al., (2015) and Salzwedel et al., (2013) after implementation of checklists.

Checklist Adoption

During post-training observations, only 6 out of 55 (11%) observations included the use of the checklist. The ACT phase of the PDSA, encourages providers to consider potential factors influencing the success of the project. The checklist was posted on the desktop of the computer workstations, often covered with other papers and not readily visible. Thus, the checklist placement on the computer stations could have negatively influenced the adoption into standard practice. A large wall posting, vertical location on the computer or personal badge tag may be more easily accessible to staff. While the author casually polled staff members for location preference, future projects may benefit from piloting options for ACT steps, such as this decision on location, before implementation.

Another potential factor contributing to the lack of adoption was staff commitment (buy-in) to checklist use. It is possible staff perceived that the benefit of checklist use did not outweigh the time it took to use the checklist. Moreover, staff may have believed that their expertise was sufficient, and the use of the checklist was

unnecessary. The author identified an issue with checklist adoption. With checklist utilization, there was an increase in the number of items transferred, 66.8% versus 88.4% (Figure 3). This increase is consistent with the literature, which shows improvements in information transfer when checklists or cognitive aids are employed (Potestio et al., 2015; Robins & Dai, 2015; Salzwedel et al., 2013). Only 2 of the 55 post-training observations included all items on the checklist, (none of the pre-training handoff observations included all items on the checklist) (Table 1). Despite the small number of complete handoffs (19/19 items), the mean number of items transferred did increase by 4% post-education/checklist initiation (Table 1). The minimal improvement in information transfer could be related to the systematic use of the checklist, increased knowledge of handoff processes from the training, or the Hawthorne effect (Polit & Beck, 2017).

It is interesting to note that the aim to improve closed-loop communication was not consistently supported by the projects pre- and post-training findings. Assessing for readiness (metric 3) decreased post training and asking, “do you have any questions” (metric 4) increased (Table 1). These findings could be because production pressure affects providers working in a fast-paced environment. Another possible factor is that providers did not make a verbal exchange signifying readiness but instead exchanged a look or other non-verbal cue to signify readiness that the observer could not consistently recognize.

Knowledge and Attitude Survey

The author employed the survey as an evaluation tool to examine the effectiveness of the training and identify future targets for QI. Caution is recommended in the interpretation of the K&A survey responses as the majority of participants choose not

to complete the surveys. Fifty-three participants completed the K&A survey before the training (response rate 27.2%), and 12 completed the survey after the training (6.2% response rate) (Table 2). Staff at a large academic medical center receive many emails of varying importance every day and may have viewed voluntary surveys as of low significance. The distribution of the post-training survey around the winter holidays may have affected response rates to this survey. The author recommends considering timing factors, allowing longer duration for responses and the potential of incentives in future projects.

Educational Training

Poor attendance at the face to face training reflects a concern with the training. Only approximately 76 of 195, (39%) attended a presentation, some arrived late, and even more left the training early. This unsatisfactory attention may be due to feelings of production pressure or lack of investment or interest in the topic. There are limitations for group meeting times due to the priority needs of patient care. Future in-services could occur more often and at varying times to better accommodate the clinical schedule. Having stakeholders and senior staff present at in-services may encourage staff to arrive on time and stay for the duration.

The attendance at the educational training varied according to the classification of the provider. This variation may have occurred for several reasons. Rotation schedules differ among providers and may have contributed to random differences in their presence at training sessions. Second, staff receive many opportunities for continuing education at academic medical centers and may not have considered handoff education as a compelling topic.

Clinical Implications

There is extensive healthcare literature regarding the need for improved communication and handoff standardization. During the implementation of this quality improvement project, the Anesthesia Patient Safety Foundation (APSF) Newsletter, the official journal of the APSF, released an edition with six articles focusing on patient handoff. Unfortunately, this QI project resulted in minimal change in staff practices, which is problematic. The urgency for improvement in information transfer in the perioperative area as noted in the APSF Newsletter calls for further QI efforts aimed at enhanced communication and handoff standardization across practice setting.

Staff working in a large academic medical facility receive copious emails, and despite having received information, all staff may not have taken the time to review its content thoroughly. All staff received education related to handoffs and checklist use via email though it is not possible to gauge how many opened or read the email information. Thus, combined with the poor attendance rates, new knowledge related to handoffs and the checklist may have been minimal. However, the setting of this project reflects rotation schedules common in current practice. Future projects may wish to consider offering training at different times and durations and including incentives to encourage attendance. Using a multimodal approach including other strategies such as simulation to improve handoff may increase the potential for improvement (Weinger et al., 2015).

This project was conducted during a period of department leadership challenges that may have influenced the commitment of senior medical staff to the project. Another distraction may have been the initiative for starting surgeries on time that preceded this project and ran concurrently. Before any future QI projects, it is important for the

department to assess these and other potential barriers. With more information, improved strategies can be developed and employed.

Implementation science identifies three factors to consider before translating evidence to practice: evidence, context, and facilitation (Randmaa et al., 2016). Future QI projects in similar academic settings may wish to closely examine the culture of the organization, leadership involvement and optimal facilitation strategies to match the needs of the situation (Randmaa et al., 2016).

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APPENDIX A

CHECKLIST

PACU Handoff Checklist	ASSESS READINESS
	Are you ready for report?
	PATIENT INFORMATION
	Name
	Age
	ID verification
	Allergies
	Diagnosis/procedure
	PMH and ASA Score
	Language preference
	ANESTHESIA MANAGEMENT
	Type of Anesthesia
	Lines/catheters
	Intake/output
	KEY POINTS
	Anesthetic events/concerns
Surgical events/concerns	
MEDICATIONS	
Analgesia plan	
Antiemetic plan	
Antibiotics	
Other medications	
CLARIFICATION	
Do you have any questions?	

Figure 3. Postanesthesia Handoff Checklist

APPENDIX B**BASELINE ORIGINAL HANDOFF KNOWLEDGE AND
ATTITUDES SURVEY**

Q1. I am the following:

- 1 CRNA
- 2 SRNA
- 3 CA-1
- 4 CA-2
- 5 CA-3
- 6 Attending Anesthesiologist

Q2. I am confident in my ability to provide an effective PACU hand-off report

- 1 Strongly disagree
- 2 Disagree
- 3 Neither agree nor disagree
- 4 Agree
- 5 Strongly agree

Q3. I have received formal training in providing a PACU hand-off report

- 1 Strongly disagree
- 2 Disagree
- 3 Neither agree nor disagree
- 4 Agree
- 5 Strongly agree

Q4. The PACU hand-off report affects patient safety

- 1 Strongly disagree
- 2 Disagree
- 3 Neither agree nor disagree
- 4 Agree
- 5 Strongly agree

Q5. The PACU hand-off report is delivered in a systematic fashion

- 1 Strongly disagree
- 2 Disagree
- 3 Neither agree nor disagree
- 4 Agree
- 5 Strongly agree

Q6. Adequate time is allotted for an effective PACU hand-off report

- 1 Strongly disagree
- 2 Disagree
- 3 Neither agree nor disagree
- 4 Agree
- 5 Strongly agree

Q7. The PACU hand-off report is delivered with minimal distractions

- 1 Strongly disagree
- 2 Disagree
- 3 Neither agree nor disagree
- 4 Agree
- 5 Strongly agree

Q8. Asking if there are any questions, comments, or concerns is an important part of the PACU hand-off report

- 1 Strongly disagree
- 2 Disagree
- 3 Neither agree nor disagree
- 4 Agree
- 5 Strongly agree

Q9. Recommendations for patient care are made clear during the PACU hand-off report

- 1 Strongly disagree
- 2 Disagree
- 3 Neither agree nor disagree
- 4 Agree
- 5 Strongly agree

APPENDIX C
OBSERVATION TOOL

(Number sequentially 1, 2,)

Time

Date

ASA_____

Type of surgery_____

Please indicate whether the following items were included in the PACU handoff report.

Q1. The anesthesia provider assessed readiness for report (e.g., "Are you ready for report?")

1 Yes or 0 No

Q2. Patient Name

1 Yes or 0 No

Q2.1. Patient Age

1 Yes or 0 No

Q3. Patient ID (band check)

1 Yes or 0 No

Q4. Allergies

1 Yes or 0 No

Q5. Diagnosis

1 Yes or 0 No

Q6. Surgical Procedure

1 Yes or 0 No

Q7. Past Medical History

1 Yes or 0 No

Q8. ASA Score

1 Yes or 0 No

Q9. Language Preference

1 Yes or 0 No

Q10. Type of Anesthesia

1 Yes or 0 No

Q11. Lines and/or catheters

1 Yes or 0 No

Q12. Intake and output

1 Yes or 0 No

Q13. Anesthetic events and/or concerns

1 Yes or 0 No

- Q14. Surgical events and/or concerns
1 Yes or 0 No
- Q15. Analgesia Plan: medications given/needed
1 Yes or 0 No
- Q16. Antiemetic Plan: medications given/needed
Yes or No
- Q17. Antibiotic Plan: medications given/needed
1 Yes or 0 No
- Q18. Other pertinent medications given/needed
1 Yes or 0 No
- Q19. Anesthesia provider offered clarifications (eg. "Do you have any questions?")
1 Yes or 0 No

APPENDIX D**ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS FOR PRE/POST-IMPLEMENTATION SURVEY**

Q10. Enter a four-digit identifier of your choice. (Answers are anonymous, they will be used for tracking purposes only. You will receive this survey again after project implementation, please make a note of your response.)

Q11. Have you completed this survey?

1 Yes, within the last 3 months

Yes, more than 3 months ago

0 No, I have not taken this survey before

Q12. I completed the handover training module (in-person lecture, or online)?

1 Yes

0 No

Q13. I gained knowledge from the training module

1 Strongly disagree

2 Disagree

3 Neither agree nor disagree

4 Agree

5 Strongly agree

Q14. I am using the checklist for handover in the PACU

1 Strongly disagree

2 Disagree

3 Neither agree nor disagree

4 Agree

5 Strongly agree

Q15. I believe the new process is effective and promotes patient safety

1 Strongly disagree

2 Disagree

3 Neither agree nor disagree

4 Agree

5 Strongly agree

APPENDIX E

STAFF PRESENTATION CONTENT

The presentation to the anesthesiology staff was a condensed version of the information in this proposal. Content included background information on the problem and the evidence-based importance of an effective standardized handoff process. Details on the planned practice change and the staff's role in the process was described. This includes the required online training and the use of the checklist when giving handoff in the PACU. There will be time allotted, five minutes, for questions and answers.

APPENDIX F
EDUCATION MODULE
PATIENT CARE HANDOFF TO THE
POSTANESTHESIA CARE UNIT
TRAINING COURSE

A SELF-DIRECTED LEARNING MODULE

INTRODUCTION:

Communication is crucial to providing safe patient care.

According to the Joint Commission on Accreditation of Healthcare Organizations (JCAHO 2003), almost 70% of all sentinel events are caused by breakdown in communication. At its core, the patient handoff is a highly complex, high stakes form of communication that directly influences patient safety. Improved handoff communication is a National Patient Safety Goal and requires accurate information regarding the patient's care, treatment, services, current condition and any recent or anticipated

changes. The Joint Commission requires handoff standardization, including an opportunity to ask and respond to questions, two-way communication (Joint Commission, 2014). A significant reduction in morbidity and mortality has been associated with the introduction of standardized processes and checklists to perioperative care transitions (Potestio et al., 2015).

This learning material is prepared to assist in educating and evaluating anesthesiology physicians, CRNAs and SRNAs who will be conducting patient care handoffs

LEARNING OBJECTIVES

At the completion of this module the participant will:

1. Define patient care handoff
2. Review the Department Policy regarding patient care handoff (remember to place link)
3. Operationalize communication strategies that can improve patient care handoff processes
4. Implement key elements of perioperative patient care handoff
5. Comprehend the impact of personal accountability in the patient care handoff
6. Understand the importance of checklist/cognitive aid utilization in handoff reporting

DEFINITIONS

Handoff Communication: The real-time process of passing patient specific information from one caregiver to another or from one team of caregivers to another for the purpose of ensuring the continuity and safety of the patient's care.

O.R. to PACU Handoff: The process of exchange of patient care information from the anesthesia provider to the post-anesthesia recovery room staff, at the end of a diagnostic, *technical* or surgical procedure.

Handoff Standardization: Ensures that the organization has defined, communicated to staff, and implemented an evidence based process whereby patient care information is communicated from one provider to another in a consistent manner, and that staff is educated regarding the process.

POLICY

Embed link (checkoff box)

Joint Commission Mandates

- Interactive communication
- Current, relevant patient information
- System to verify received information
- Time and opportunity for the receiving practitioner to verify information
- Uninterrupted communication between practitioners

Operationalize communication strategies that can improve patient care handoff processes

Timely communication	The CRNA keeps team members in the loop; communicates as close to the event(s) as possible.
Collaborative communication	The CRNA elicits team member input; approaches problems in a team fashion

Closed loop communication	The CRNA clarifies and confirms what is discussed, requested, and/or completed.
Direct communication	The CRNA communicates with clarity and purpose to a specific person.
Communicates with appropriate tone/volume	The CRNA is aware of his/her verbal and nonverbal communication patterns; does not speak too loud or too soft; speaks in a non-threatening tone.

TRANSPORT FROM O.R. TO PACU

The patient should be stable prior to admission to PACU. If not, the transfer should be postponed until adequate stabilization and/or appropriate admitting location have been attained. The circulating nurse shall call ahead to the PACU to give a brief report after collaborating with the anesthesia provider. Once the PACU is ready, the anesthesia provider can prepare for transport by doing the following:

- Verify > 500cc oxygen in the O2 tank
- Elevate the head of the bed as indicated
- Remove monitors when safe to do so
- Move the patient from O.R. table to gurney utilizing safe technique (e.g. Spine and/or safety precautions, being careful not to dislodge drains/dressings)
- Place the patient on 8-10 liters/minute of oxygen
- Reconcile and/or bring controlled medications with you
- Transport patient while maintaining direct visualization of the patient's head and chest at all times and perform airway/breathing assessments as necessary

ADMIT TO THE PACU

Upon admission ensure that the patient is properly connected to the monitor, if PACU nurse is not ready attach monitors and evaluate the patient.

- **Assess respiratory status** and treat compromise such as obstruction, secretions, hypopnea, wheezing, stridor or insufficiency related to inadequate reversal
- **Assess cardiovascular system** for any abnormalities such as hypo/hypertension, dysrhythmias or evidence of ischemia or injury
- **Assess temperature** and treat hyper or hypothermia
- Institute treatment as necessary

CONDUCT THE PATIENT HANDOFF REPORT

- **ASSESS READINESS**
 - *Are you ready for report?*
- **PATIENT INFORMATION**
 - *Name*
 - *Age*
 - *ID verification*
 - *Allergies*
 - *Diagnosis/procedure*
 - *PMH & ASA Score*

- *Language preference*
- **ANESTHESIA MANAGEMENT**
 - *Type of Anesthesia*
 - *Lines/catheters*
 - *Intake/output*
- **KEY POINTS**
 - *Anesthetic events/concerns*
 - *Surgical events/concerns*
- **MEDICATIONS**
 - *Analgesic plan*
 - *Antiemetic plan*
 - *Antibiotics*
 - *Other medications*
- **CLARIFICATION**
 - *Do you have any questions?*
- **DOCUMENT HANDOFF IN RECORD**

ASSESS READINESS

With the patient chart available and/or electronic medical record (EMR) opened to the proper patient, ask the qualified person receiving report to identify themselves, and

- Assess their readiness (verbal acknowledgement, “are you ready for report”)
- Ensure that the environment is quiet and uninterrupted
- Maintain face to face contact with the receiver (PACU RN and anesthesiology personnel)

PATIENT INFORMATION

- **Patient name**
Be sure to identify the patient by using their name not just a procedure. Using the name is a form of personalization as well as one of three patient identifiers.
- **Patient age**
- **Patient ID verification**
Checking the patient ID bracelet should be done by the PACU RN
- **Allergies**
List allergies and include reactions
- **Diagnosis/procedure**
Be sure to identify the reason for surgery, including, for example, mechanism of injury and other acute co-existing conditions.
- **PMH and ASA Score**
ASA Score
Indicates patient’s acuity level
Include all relevant past medical and surgical history

For example, if patient has a history of hypertension, include the following:

Controlled or uncontrolled

Baseline blood pressure

Meds: preoperative and intraoperative

Other information to consider including

Baseline vital signs if relevant (e.g. Baseline tachycardia)

Baseline labs if relevant (e.g., K⁺ or Hgb/Hct)

Baseline activity (e.g. cane, walker, etc.)

Limb restrictions (e.g. avoid NIBP cuff on same arm as lymph node dissection, AV shunt, or flap)

Baseline cognitive function (e.g. confusion, affect)

Include relevant social history

For example, IVDA, cocaine, marijuana use etc.

- **Language preference**

It requires higher cognitive processes to speak in a non-native language which can be difficult for someone emerging from anesthesia

ANESTHESIA MANAGEMENT

- **Type of Anesthesia**

Include whether general endotracheal anesthesia (GETA), laryngeal mask airway (LMA), monitored anesthesia care (MAC), or regional anesthesia (RA) was utilized

- **Lines/catheters**

IVs, a-lines, central lines, foley catheter, chest tubes and any additional drains

- **Intake/output**

IV fluids, blood products, EBL, and UOP

Other relevant output (e.g. NGT, drains)

MEDICATIONS (intraoperative and postoperative)*

- **Analgesia plan**

Administered, anticipated and ordered

- **Antiemetic plan**

Administered, anticipated and ordered

- **Antibiotics**

Name, dosage and time. Include if any scheduled antibiotics are due while in PACU

- **Other pertinent medications**

Muscle relaxant/reversal, if there is concern for residual weakness

Antihypertensives, steroids

KEY POINTS

- Anesthetic events/concerns

Consider intraoperative course and what will be relevant to post-operative management (e.g. Difficult airway with potential for obstruction, hypo/hypertension which may require treatment postoperatively).

- Surgical events/concerns
Report any signs or symptoms to watch for that the patient may present.
(e.g., Steep Trendelenburg with potential for airway edema, excessive blood loss necessitating labs or additional monitoring)

CLARIFICATION

- Do you have any questions?
Utilize two-way communication (closed loop communication)
Re-assess patient condition and confirm PACU nurse is prepared to accept care of the patient before departing

DOCUMENT HANDOFF IN RECORD

Complete the anesthesia documentation including documentation of patient care handoff to PACU RN and finalize the record.

Comprehend the impact of personal accountability in the patient care handoff
Understand the importance of checklist/cognitive aid utilization in handoff reporting